

PARADOXICAL IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS IN DEFENCE, CYBER SECURITY AND MEDIA DIMENSIONS

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly becoming a key catalyst for transformation within the international system. AI offers both significant potential and serious risks, compelling nations to balance extraordinary opportunities with major challenges. The primary goal of this paper is to analyse and present how AI technologies and their paradoxical socio-technical nature are transforming international relations by accelerating global instability and security threats, and creating new vectors of power, vulnerability, and influence. The paper examines transformative impacts in three critical dimensions: defence, cyber-security, and media. In the defence dimension, we show that emerging autonomous systems across all domains will significantly enhance national warfare capabilities, but will also reinforce strategic competition among states, with episodic live tests in conflicts, and increase the strategic dependency of less capable states. AI will also create more powerful offensive and defensive cyber tools, generating a new cyber-security dilemma, increasing the likelihood of new conflicts, and empowering non-state criminal actors. Additionally, in the media dimension, AI will automate and amplify the production, distribution, and consumption of information and disinformation during peace, crisis, and wartime, influencing public opinion and discourse, and exposing democratic states to informational, political, and diplomatic conflicts with potentially serious effects on inter-state trust and stability.

Key words: artificial intelligence; international relations; defence; cyber-security; media.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Advancements in technology and related innovations have gradually and profoundly affected the dynamics of international relations (IR), the power of states, and their national interests. Artificial intelligence (AI), with its ability to perform tasks associated with intelligent beings – demonstrated by an increasing number of expert systems (applied AI) and general intelligence systems (AGI) – will transform all aspects of human life, including international relations. The adoption of AI systems in decision-making, threat and risk assessment, intelligence, warfare, logistics, weapons production, learning, and trading makes this technology a strategic imperative for all ambitious states. The ability to develop advanced AI systems is often equated with technological sovereignty and national prestige. Major powers, especially the USA and China, invest heavily in AI research as part of a broader competition for global leadership.

The modern world results from the continuous interplay between technological and organisational changes, including innovations. Technological development has demonstrated remarkable transformative potential through three well-known technological revolutions: the steam engine as the basis for the first revolution, electricity and mass assembly lines for the second, and computers and Internet for the third. Artificial intelligence has been recognised as another uniquely transformative technology and the foundation for the fourth revolution, with the potential to change everything. We consider AI a technology of self-adaptive learning with varying levels of independence from human operators and decision-makers, and with extremely high potential to transform most technical, analytical, and decision-making areas, including international relations and related competitive and cooperative processes among all actors. In this paper, we show that the transformative role of AI in international relations may be most effectively illustrated by considering three strategic dimensions: defence, cyber-security, and media. We argue that AI will increasingly play a paradoxical role in international relations by simultaneously producing positive outcomes and less controlled negative effects on relations among key actors. Specifically, AI and the race to adopt it have begun to unleash competitive forces among states for efficiency, influence, and power across several dimensions, including the potential for more destructive conflicts. At the same time, traditional Westphalian state sovereignty is being further eroded by large AI companies that are accumulating knowledge on how to develop, produce, and manage AI systems.

In the defence dimension, emerging autonomous systems in all domains – including decision-making, intelligence, targeting, logistics, training, and electronic warfare – will significantly enhance national warfare capabilities, but will also reinforce strategic competition among states, with episodic live tests in conflicts (such as Ukraine), and increase the strategic asymmetric dependency of less capable states. This also leads to new ethical and legal risks, including the proliferation of AI technology to malicious non-state actors. In the cyber-security dimension, AI will create more powerful offensive and defensive cyber tools, generating a new cyber-security dilemma, increasing the likelihood of new conflicts, and empowering non-state criminal actors in their activities (Luknar 2024a). Additionally, AI use in the media dimension will automate and amplify the production, distribution, and consumption of information and disinformation during peace, crisis, and wartime, influencing public opinion and discourse, and exposing democratic states to informational, political, and diplomatic conflicts with serious potential effects on inter-state trust and stability. The public sphere risks becoming a more automated media battlespace in the future.

These three dimensions illustrate the multifaceted ways in which AI will function as a tool, a strategic vector, and a new source of challenges in global politics and international relations. The presence of AI as both a resourceful tool and a vector of rivalry points to a specific socio-technical paradox that will inevitably affect international relations. The dual nature of AI will simultaneously offer opportunities for advancing human cooperation (e.g. in politics and international relations) and avenues for more or less intense competition among actors. In other words, it will also become a significant source of instability. Scholars (Brooks 1980, 65; Dahlke 2024) suggest that technology should be understood as a socio-technical construct, rather than being viewed as purely technical. This is especially true for AI, which redefines conventional frameworks of control, responsibility, and governance.

This paper first identifies and analyses the opening of Pandora's box in international relations by demonstrating the paradoxical nature of AI. Second, it focuses on three unique dimensions – defence, cyber-security, and media – to present more concrete examples of effects on international relations. We link the paradoxical effects of artificial intelligence with realist theory (Waltz 1979) in the military dimension, constructivist theory (Onuf 1989; Wendt 1992) in the media dimension, and security dilemma theory in the cyber security dimension (Herz 1950; Jervis 1978; Johnson 2023). Finally, we provide a comparative categorisation of AI's positive and negative effects on these three dimensions.

2 AI-INDUCED OPENING OF PANDORA'S BOX IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

Several scholars have described Artificial Intelligence as a technology that exists at the intersection of imagination and singularity (Vinge 1993; Kurzweil 1999; Jin, Nicholas and Ghassan 2025). Although this technology has been evolving since the 1950s, it has only recently become 'visible' through increased efficiency, production, and consumption (Лукнап 2024b). The Greek myth of Pandora provides the best illustration of how AI could shape the future trajectory of international relations. Zeus gave her a sealed container (box) with instructions never to open it. Pandora, known for her curiosity, opened it, releasing all existing evils, plagues, and misfortunes into the world. In the modern context of AI, this story symbolises a situation where seemingly small acts of socio-technical progress unwittingly unleash a multitude of unwanted consequences.

Advancements in Artificial Intelligence are already influencing, and will continue to influence, international relations in significant ways. They have become an inevitable part of national security agendas in the global technological race. However, these efforts towards technological advancement are simultaneously perceived as security threats by other nations. At the national level, AI advancements serve to improve security and efficiency for specific countries, but not necessarily for global well-being. Such "short-term" winning strategies for some countries have gradually become a force that continuously fuels the technology race, or technologically-based security race, among nations.

Several countries (USA, China, UK, Canada, EU, Japan, South Korea, Singapore, India, UAE, Israel, Australia, Russia, etc.) have already incorporated AI into their strategic agendas. Each advancement in AI boosts worldwide technological competition and further accelerates the global technological race, while security and defence challenges remain unresolved. Bremmer and Suleyman have

stressed that, across countries, AI will be the focus of intensive geopolitical competition. AI supremacy, or the competition for AI supremacy, will be a strategic objective for every government with the resources to compete. The two key players, the US and China, view AI development as a zero-sum game that will give the winner a decisive strategic edge in the future (Bremmer and Suleyman 2023, 7–8). Nations and organisations best able to anticipate and exploit technological opportunities will likely have a decisive advantage in future competitions, crises, and conflicts. AI will also be the linchpin for achieving military superiority through the use of data – transforming it into relevant information, usable knowledge, and ultimately decision advantage (Thiele 2021, 59). All systems will be used in the pursuit of power. Schmidt et al. fear that all AI tools will become weapons of first resort in future conflicts (Schmidt et al 2021, cited in Thiele 2021, 76). The ability to innovate in this field has become synonymous with international influence, national power, economic competitiveness, political legitimacy, military power and even internal security (Raska and Bitzinger 2023, 2).

The growing importance and use of AI in military and security applications raises several challenges (Prezelj 2024a) and risks in everyday life (Luknar 2024a; Luknar 2025a). These challenges range from various strategic and operational risks to numerous ethical and legal risks, including the danger of uncontrolled and unstoppable development of general AI (Prezelj 2024a). Luberisse (2023, 5–9) wrote an informative book on the geopolitics of AI, in which he addressed its impact on international stability and the risk of accidental use. According to him, the main problem is the geopolitical risk leading to a power struggle between great powers, with implications for the balance of global power.

According to Luberisse (2023), the AI power struggle refers to the ongoing competition among great powers to develop and deploy advanced AI technologies in their military and intelligence operations. This competition is driven by the potential of AI to fundamentally alter the balance of power in the international system. Great powers such as the USA, China, Russia, and several European countries are actively investing in AI to gain an advantage in this ongoing power struggle. These investments include funding AI research and development, deploying AI in military and intelligence operations, and developing AI-powered weapons and surveillance systems. Soare (2023, 81) also stressed that the frontrunners of the global revolution in military affairs, the USA and China, are engaged in a race to adopt AI and other emerging and disruptive technologies. Other authors believe that the USA, Russia, and China have entered a modern-day Space Race-style competition to develop and harness artificial intelligence technologies (Roth 2019).

AI development is often described as driven by capitalist imperatives. As a result, “technology has an impact that goes against people’s interests and deprives them of their autonomy” (Winkel 2025, 1949). While AI is frequently praised for its many benefits, critical perspectives suggest these advantages come with hidden geopolitical, security, and social consequences (Luknar 2025b). Economic changes cannot be ignored. PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC)’s Global Artificial Intelligence Study projects that AI will significantly transform global productivity and GDP, adding “up to \$15.7 trillion” (PwC 2020, 3) to the world economy by 2030, largely by increasing efficiency, productivity, and consumption. This technology represents a potentially uncontrollable force shaped by profit and political interests (Winkel 2025). We are witnessing a fundamental power shift, as technology giants, rather than sovereign states, now control essential resources such as specialised talent, massive datasets, and vast computational power necessary for AI development. Consequently, a critical dependency has

emerged, with governments reliant on a few technology companies to access AI capabilities considered crucial for national economic competitiveness and security. As a result, these corporations now exercise substantial geopolitical power over governments, frequently operating as entities that can shape international norms and global standards according to their own interests, even when these conflict with nation-state policies. This may affect societal progress; nevertheless, technological advancements can also alter dynamics among countries (Branch 2018). As AI becomes a central tool of statecraft, nations that do not build their own technological capacity or regulatory sovereignty risk becoming data colonies. The consequences of this dynamic are becoming exponentially more complex over time, as we have not yet regulated all AI issues. This positions AI advancements as both a source of power and a source of tension and security threats. The chain reaction triggered by technological development has already begun, and Pandora's box is opening.

The Westphalian state model (Gross 1948) of national "sovereignty" is being eroded. The algorithms that shape what citizens see (public discourse via social media), how the economy functions (via financial and logistics AI), and national security (via cybersecurity, autonomous weapons, and other systems) are created and often operated by large foreign technology companies. These companies are not subject to national laws in the same way as domestic entities. Therefore, a foreign power, through one of its corporations, can exert significant influence within another country, challenging that country's ability to control its own destiny. We will present the early beginnings of such changes through three key dimensions based on recent developments on the international scene.

3 THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DEFENCE: TRANSFORMING MILITARY POWER AND STRATEGY WITH PARTIALLY CONTROLLED EFFECTS

Technological capabilities play a direct role in determining how effectively countries can succeed in warfare. Among policymakers and analysts, a prevailing belief is emerging that artificial intelligence will bring about a revolution in military affairs, with significant potential to reshape the structure of the international system (Flournoy 2023; Ackerman and Stavridis 2024; Burdette et al 2025).

Major powers in modern society are seeking AI dominance, operating under the strategic assumption that technological superiority is key to future military pre-eminence. While investment continues, the integration of AI into military structures remains limited at present. Current systems offer only limited autonomy and are used in very restricted scenarios. Most ground robots are tele-operated, while military unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) possess only basic functions such as automated navigation, still relying heavily on human control for mission execution. States often use low-cost technologies combined with new approaches to warfare to replace high-cost technologies based on outdated methods. Countries worldwide have recognised AI as an essential tool in the modern military industry; however, they paradoxically do not have equal development dynamics, budgets, access to AI tools, or a sufficient number of expert personnel for AI application in defence. These paradoxical effects can be clearly aligned with the foundational assumptions of realist theory (see Waltz 1979), which holds that governments develop military capabilities as rational instruments to advance national security and strengthen their relative power. Global powers are focused on transforming AI potential into actionable military

tools. The use of AI may serve as a path to military dominance, which can be outlined in seven steps:

- 1) **Autonomous Systems.** For example, China's military (PLA) is developing UAVs, ground vehicles, and underwater drones for reconnaissance missions, logistical support, and swarm operations. These technologies are likely to rely on AI for both autonomous manoeuvring and tactical decisions. Key achievements include swarm-capable drones and unmanned surface vessels (USVs) such as the JARI model (The China Briefing 2025).
- 2) **Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR).** AI-powered ISR systems process massive datasets in real-time to improve situational awareness. Machine learning enables faster analysis of satellite imagery for target detection. The PLA has invested in geospatial analysis platforms comparable to U.S. systems, such as Descartes Labs, but adapted for its own military requirements. Integrating AI into military operations promises significant gains in situational awareness through advanced data processing. For example, the U.S. military used an AI image classifier to scan large intelligence datasets to detect objects such as vehicles, directly supporting counter-ISIS operations (Scharre 2023, 56–58). A key advantage lies in AI's capacity to process information on a scale and at a speed impossible for humans.
- 3) **Command and Control (C3).** The integration of AI into military and strategic domains enhances data-driven decision-making. AI-driven decision-support systems improve battlefield coordination by fusing information from diverse sources. The PLA is developing "command brains" designed to help commanders make swift decisions in complex environments.
- 4) **Logistics and Predictive Maintenance.** With AI tools, supply chains can be optimised and equipment breakdowns predicted before they occur. One application is the creation of intelligent warehouses that improve logistical operations.
- 5) **Simulation and Training.** Generative AI is used in wargaming and training simulations to prepare troops for "intelligentised" warfare, with particular emphasis on multi-drone swarm simulation systems.
- 6) **Electronic Warfare.** AI enhances radar target detection, signal classification, and electromagnetic spectrum operations, playing an essential role in neutralising adversary technologies in challenging operational environments.
- 7) **Automatic Target Recognition (ATR).** Advances in ATR use machine learning to quickly, precisely, and reliably identify threats even in noisy or complex environments.

AI is becoming a strategic imperative, but access to and capacity for its exploitation are extremely and paradoxically unequal. This is most evident in the division among modern countries regarding their investments in the application and development of AI. Projections indicate that the AI in military market will expand significantly, from USD 9.2 billion in 2023 to USD 38.8 billion by 2028, reflecting a compound annual growth rate of 33.3% (Research and Markets 2023). Amid this rapid growth, the US Department of Defense (DoD) is making a strategic effort to lead this technological transformation, as shown by its allocation of USD 1.8 billion in 2024 and 2025 (Vincent 2024). Starting at USD 7.9 billion in 2022, the global AI in the military market is projected to reach USD 11.4 billion in 2025 (Pangakar 2025). Also other countries with strong financial and technological bases, such as Russia, Israel, the United Kingdom and the EU, are leading the adoption of this technology as its defence applications expand. Israel, for example, excels at integrating AI into intelligence and precision weapons, while the EU is addressing the gap through collaborative initiatives. Ambitious developing countries such as India, Turkey, Brazil, Singapore, and many others

recognise the importance of AI and are investing in it, but they lack the scale of funding or the technological capabilities of the leading powers. They often focus on specific niches (e.g., AI-enabled drones) or on purchasing technology. A significant segment of the global community simply does not have the financial, technological, or human capacity for serious military AI development. This can lead to new forms of strategic dependency on more technologically advanced allies or arms suppliers.

Accessibility is hindered not only by financial limitations but also by strict export controls imposed by governments concerned about the safety of sophisticated AI algorithms, data sets, and hardware. Civilian AI innovations, from image recognition to autonomous driving, are easily adapted for military applications such as target detection and unmanned drones. As a result, many countries restrict the sale of the most advanced AI tools and equipment. Relying on cloud services or hardware from a major foreign provider can leave a country vulnerable during sanctions or geopolitical tensions. This vulnerability drives the pursuit of technological sovereignty and the creation of domestic alternatives, further stimulating international competition. Countries are increasingly unwilling to depend on foreign platforms.

The rise of AI in military applications has intensified strategic competition between the United States and China, as both nations seek technological dominance in defence capabilities. The PLA has become a central actor in driving global military modernisation. Guided by its New Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan and the broader objective of “intelligentised” warfare, China aims to become a global AI leader by 2030 and to build a world-class military by 2049. To achieve this, the PLA is prioritising technological superiority in future conflicts through AI-enabled autonomous systems, battlefield awareness, logistics, and decision-making capabilities. China’s significant investment and progress in military AI over the past several years have raised concerns within the US national security establishment (Bresnick 2024a; Metz 2018). “US government leaders and defence industry insiders have sounded the alarm about China’s advances in AI, and some now claim that China is outpacing the United States in developing and fielding AI-enabled military systems” (Bresnick 2024b). According to Chinese military strategies, the AI is viewed as a tool to merge diverse data sources into actionable datasets for advanced analysis. It is however unclear whether the Chinese military possesses sufficient technologically skilled workforce needed to create world-class AI military systems. The PLA’s centralised decision-making processes may inhibit its ability to leverage AI-enabled decision-support systems (Bresnick 2024b).

The battlefield in Ukraine has become a live laboratory for AI-driven military infrastructure. Ukraine, supported by the United States and Europe, has deployed AI-enhanced drones, computer vision for precision targeting, and machine learning for analysing satellite data to forecast Russian troop activity. Russia, in response, has tested AI-powered electronic warfare systems, loitering munitions, and automated battlefield technologies. The Ukraine war demonstrates that AI is no longer a peripheral technology but a fundamental tool for reshaping the dynamics of the modern battlefield.

Across the Middle East and beyond, countries such as Israel, Turkey, and the UAE are pushing AI-powered drones and defence systems into global markets. Israel’s Iron Dome integrates AI for real-time threat identification and more effective interception (BBC 2024). Turkey’s Bayraktar drones, equipped with AI-supported targeting systems, have been deployed in Ukraine and Africa, shifting military balances and intensifying international competition over drone exports

(ADF 2025). Meanwhile, Gulf states are investing heavily in AI defence technologies, often in partnership with US and Chinese firms, turning the Middle East into a focal point of AI-military rivalry and proliferation.

The development of lethal autonomous weapons simultaneously creates serious ethical and security dilemmas, including the limited capacity of AI systems to understand and apply international humanitarian law. AI systems raise concerns about their ability to adhere to the principles of distinction and proportionality in combat. Operationally, the “black box” problem can lead to overconfidence in AI systems and incomprehensible decisions, while their narrow training experience increases the risk of decisions with questionable validity. Furthermore, the strategic landscape is threatened by the lower threshold for the use of AI-powered force and the easy proliferation of this technology to malicious state and non-state actors (Prezelj 2024b, 389–390).

If one thinks within a realist framework (e.g. see Waltz 1979), AI advancement leaves states no choice but to acquire AI capabilities for military purposes. Acquisition of AI will create a gap between nations, which can have far-reaching consequences for global security and the balance of power, while also leading to new global realignments. A lack of AI can make a conventional military vulnerable and related countries weak. With advanced AI, actors can undermine an adversary’s superior numbers or technology through tactics such as communication jamming, system hacking, or swarming inexpensive autonomous drones. Less developed countries become dependent on imported military technology that includes AI, leaving them more open to influence. The paradoxical nature of AI is most evident in defence, where it serves simultaneously as a strategic asset and a source of tension and rivalry. We are witnessing a major shift in power from governments to technology giants who control essential resources, experts, and datasets. Technology giants are new actors on the international stage who influence international relations and drive AI in the military, even when these actions conflict with nation-state policies. The militarisation of AI is redefining the nature of conflict, while technology companies seek to protect their interests, which may or may not align with state policies, greatly undermining peace and stability.

4 THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN CYBER-SECURITY: SHAPING GLOBAL THREATS AND PROTECTIONS WITH SPIRAL CONSEQUENCES

The integration of Artificial Intelligence into national security is fundamentally reshaping the speed and scale of cyber operations, enabling new forms of espionage, surveillance and other offensive or defensive capabilities, such as proactive threat detection and prevention, phishing and fraud detection, vulnerability management, security automation and orchestration (SOAR), behavioural analytics, etc. The capacity of AI algorithms to analyse massive datasets and real-time user digital interactions allows the uncovering of subtle anomalies and patterns that signal potential cyber intrusions, thereby surpassing the limitations of conventional signature-based defences. The application of machine learning also improves the identification of sophisticated social engineering attempts by critically examining electronic messages for markers of deception, including suspicious phraseology and counterfeit web pages. In safeguarding critical assets, AI performs autonomous scans of digital environments to discover, locate, and rank security weaknesses. These defensive capabilities are enhanced by orchestrated response systems, where AI enables

real-time countermeasures against detected threats, dramatically reducing response times and allowing human specialists to focus on complex threat assessment. AI also employs ongoing behavioural analysis to build adaptive models of typical operations across the digital environment, enabling immediate alerts to significant anomalies that may indicate a security incident.

The integration of AI into cybersecurity frameworks yields substantial offensive operational benefits. However, these advantages are paradoxically escalating significant challenges for international relations, potentially initiating a dangerous spiral of consequences. National efforts to apply AI for defensive superiority, enabling proactive countermeasures and superior operational control, simultaneously accelerate competition for more advanced capabilities. AI advancement appears as a destabilising factor, creating new vulnerabilities and avenues for state-on-state conflict. Interpreted through the lens of classical security dilemma literature, AI development has introduced new uncertainties, leading to a vicious spiral. Worldwide, states feel they inevitably need “self-help” (see Herz 1950) promised through AI, altering “the offence-defence balance” (see Jervis 1978, 187). Johnson (2023) also employed this classic security dilemma theory to explain how AI effects heighten uncertainties, insecurities, and mistrust within strategically competitive relations.

AI advancements have resulted in the development of smarter cyberattacks and the emergence of new serious threats that demand detection and response. This leads to a race for AI tools and compels experts to address more complex issues related to AI risks and attacks. Consequently, existing international laws and norms struggle to keep pace with the ethical and strategic challenges posed by autonomous systems. This technological shift is creating a more complex and unpredictable global security environment, where strategic advantage is increasingly defined by algorithmic dominance. Modern society faces fear, tension, and technological competition at the international level. This creates also a transparency deficit, complicating the demands for regulatory frameworks, international compliance, and post-incident analysis.

In this chapter, we synthetically outline some critical examples of cyberattacks that have occurred since 2009 to demonstrate the ongoing competition, or even conflict, among key global powers in cyberspace. Beginning around 2009, the advanced group known as APT1 executed a large-scale cyber espionage campaign, compromising at least 141 companies and organisations, primarily in the West. The campaign’s main objective was industrial espionage, and substantial evidence points to the group’s origins in China (National Security Archive, 2013). On the other hand, documents from the Snowden leaks reveal that the US National Security Agency (NSA) systematically targeted China’s top-tier Tsinghua University. Tsinghua houses one of the country’s six major backbone networks, CERNET, which serves millions of users across hundreds of universities. This demonstrates that Western intelligence agencies have also engaged in sophisticated cyber operations against high-value Chinese targets, including those in the academic sector (Gellman and Soltani 2013). This cyberattack leveraged a sophisticated “computer network exploitation” (CNE) system, which automates the infiltration of foreign networks for computer espionage. CNE involves gaining access to computer systems and retrieving data (Monte 2015, 1) in pursuit of mission objectives. While the specific tools are classified, such a system inherently relies on AI and machine learning for tasks such as automated vulnerability scanning, pattern recognition to identify valuable data, and managing large-scale intrusions with minimal human intervention.

A range of other cyberattacks showed that lists of employees, technology development and system vulnerabilities can be a valuable target (e.g. Chinese operation against the US Office of Personnel Management, American operation “Shotgiant” against Huawei (Congressional Research Service 2015; BBC 2014; Rayman 2014; Sanger and Perloth 2014)). Some other attacks focused more on corrupting data and disrupting critical systems, such as NotPetya, a Russian-attributed attack in 2017 that used disruptive malware disguised as ransomware (Wolff 2021). Third cluster of attacks focused on payment, internet and television services (see the attack by Ukraine’s military intelligence on Russia’s SPB fast payment system, a platform used for transferring funds in support of war, denying also internet and television services to hundreds of thousands, and causing economic damages of up to \$30 million (Hodunova 2025)). Critical information infrastructures have also been targeted from all sides, aiming to obtain sensitive information, spread instability, and cause disruption in communication systems, and essential infrastructure (e.g. attack on SolarWinds’ software platform Orion to obtain access to networks of program users (Center for Internet Security 2021; Temple-Raston 2021). Stuxnet is another example, representing a class of highly complex cyber weapon. It was reportedly developed jointly by the United States and Israel (Sanger 2012) as a malicious computer worm. Its primary function was the physical sabotage of industrial infrastructure, specifically Iran’s nuclear centrifuges in their nuclear enrichment programme. The worm deliberately caused the facility’s centrifuges to spin unpredictably and self-destruct while feeding normal operating data to plant monitors, thereby crippling Iran’s nuclear programme while concealing the cause of the damage. While Stuxnet did not contain self-learning AI algorithms as we know them today, its programmed adaptive behaviour (searching for the right target, exploiting up to four unknown zero-day vulnerabilities in existing computer systems), deceptive behaviour (ability to send false reports to controllers), and unprecedented complexity make it one of the most sophisticated cyber weapons ever made and a true precursor to a new generation of AI cyber weapons.

It appears that many of these incidents (such as APT1, Stuxnet, NotPetya, etc.) were probably launched by government organisations with substantial resources, while others were initiated by criminal actors. These attacks typically affected multiple victims, causing significant inconvenience and, in many cases, substantial financial damage to the affected individuals or organisations. We can also observe growing complexity of cyber-attack tools and methods from relatively simple attacks, exploiting known vulnerabilities, to advanced threats (Stuxnet) and supply chain compromises (SolarWinds case), and finally to AI-driven independent polymorphic (mutating) malware, autonomously exploring the victims’ networks, adapting autonomously in real-time, misleading enemy’s AI defences, learning from past experiences, etc.

The paradoxical technical nature of AI in the cyber domain, however, shows that AI tools are used not only for attacking (AI-powered offense), but also for defending against non-AI and AI-supported threats (AI-powered defence). In other words, “the role of AI is central to achieving a modern, resilient cybersecurity posture” (Edwards 2025, 97). The Director of the US AI Center stated that we are going to be shocked by the speed, chaos, and bloodiness in the future, as wars and conflicts will be fought by algorithms against algorithms (Rickli and Mantellassi 2023, 20). Additionally, adaptive AI learning systems are designed to customise training to specific team responsibilities and to live threats, aligning adversary tactics with appropriate defensive strategies.

Furthermore, AI systems enable the development of dynamic simulations that challenge security measures to their limits and offer valuable insights for continuous improvement. One such model is MITRE ATT&CK, which stands for Adversarial Tactics, Techniques, and Common Knowledge, created by the MITRE Corporation. The model builds upon knowledge that combines the methods used by adversaries to help defend against persistent threats. By focusing on real attacker patterns, it serves as a guide to help organisations better predict, identify, and respond to cyberattacks more efficiently. A complementary framework that “already provides a robust structure for defensive tactics and techniques” (Edwards 2025, 101) is MITRE DEFEND. Its primary purpose is to mitigate damage more proactively, disrupting and deterring adversaries before they can inflict significant harm. The model is continually improving by integrating feedback and adapting in real-time to address emerging threats. In other words, current observations are likely to improve as the model refines its capability to address modern threats.

The integration of artificial Intelligence is fundamentally and gradually changing the framework for achieving cybersecurity. AI produces a contradictory outcome in cybersecurity by simultaneously strengthening both opposing sides. It enables nations to automate defence against various cyberattacks, identify risks, and analyse threats more efficiently and at unprecedented speed. However, malicious actors also use AI to generate sophisticated cyberattacks. This creates a relentless need for cybersecurity feedback. The paradoxical effects of AI use will create and fuel a specific cybersecurity dilemma, where one state’s defensive AI is perceived as a threat by another state, and vice versa. This will induce significant interstate uncertainties about existing capabilities and intentions, consequently leading to a lack of trust (see Prezelj 2024a). AI leads to rapidly escalating tendencies for continuous and automatic improvement of offensive and defensive measures. The same algorithmic efficiency that secures networks also lowers the barrier for launching large-scale, sophisticated attacks. Furthermore, AI systems themselves will become lucrative targets, creating a new critical vulnerability surface. Ultimately, the technology developed to create a more secure environment inherently introduces new and potent threats. AI-driven competition among states will consequently intensify and create new layers of strategic instability and competition among nations.

5 THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MEDIA DIMENSION: REDEFINING INFLUENCE IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

A classic debate in media studies has been the tension between the idealistic-humanistic approach, which characterises international communication as a means of bringing nations and peoples together to increase mutual understanding and world peace, and the political proselytisation approach, which sees international communication as a tool for propaganda, ideological confrontation, advertising, and the creation of myths and clichés (Mowlana 1997, 6, 169). This dichotomy is also reflected in debates on democratic and autocratic communication futures, where serious concerns have been expressed that new technology might not only bring about the democratisation of the communication process, but also several negative effects (Vreg 1990, 11, 324). In these debates, the communication revolution can, from an optimistic perspective, provide solutions to human problems or, alternatively, create new conflicts and crises. Modern states share a theoretical vision for adopting AI in the media sector to foster efficiency through new creative expressions and personalised content.

Public understanding of artificial intelligence is largely articulated and contested within various media sources. The media plays a crucial role in shaping and defining the visibility and sentiments towards AI for public consumption (Nah et al 2020). A well-established pattern in media discourse is the oscillation between utopian and dystopian extremes of AI. This dualistic narrative of salvation versus threat, extensively documented by scholars, directly influences public perception and regulatory debates surrounding the technology.

The application of AI in media may fundamentally transform the mechanisms of international relations within the global community. Onuf (1989; 2013) argued that people inhabit a social reality they create through social interactions, emphasising that social structures and power relations are socially constructed as outcomes of our collective actions and practices. From a constructivist perspective, the integration of artificial intelligence into global media systems produces deeply paradoxical effects that fundamentally reshape and socially reconstruct international political reality in a process that is both similar to and different from that described by Wendt (1992, 1999). The media significantly influences public opinion (Entman 2004) and how governments interpret international risks, opportunities, and policy directions (Robinson 2002; Gilboa 2005). At the same time, critical theorists argue that the media tends to uphold dominant power relations by giving preference to specific narratives while minimising alternatives (Herman and Chomsky 1988). Digital media has further complicated international relations by enabling transnational activism, disinformation campaigns, and new forms of soft power (Nye 2011). Overall, the literature shows that the media is not merely a channel of information but a dynamic actor that shapes global political processes. AI systems are increasingly utilised to automate content production, personalise news distribution, and analyse audience engagement, thereby enhancing efficiency and scalability. However, this technological integration also introduces significant challenges, including the potential for embedding and amplifying societal biases found in training data. The study “The Whiteness of AI” (Cave and Dihal 2020) demonstrates that major search engines, when users search for terms such as “artificial intelligence” or “robot”, typically return stock images overwhelmingly racialised as White, as these tools both mirror and reinforce pre-existing societal biases within their datasets. This algorithmic curation reinforces the association between intelligence, professionalism, and Whiteness for a global audience. Consequently, this biased representation can perpetuate a harmful cycle by influencing public perception, steering research funding, and shaping policy debates around AI to focus on the risks and opportunities for White, middle-class demographics, while marginalising people of colour (Cave and Dihal 2020, 691–693, 699–700). This is only one example confirming that technology platforms not only provide certain services or information; they may also perpetuate existing inequalities or compromise journalistic integrity. Beyond the implementation of AI in media services lies the purpose or directive (input, data, information) that often embodies the institutional authority of the AI tool creator or user. The implemented data content and directives in a given AI system are often good indicators of the investment and policy priorities of its creators.

The strategic use of artificial intelligence, such as social bots and automated accounts, enables the manipulation of digital information flows, thereby threatening democratic integrity and corrupting the public sphere. This degradation of information integrity has profound implications for democratic governance and introduces a critical vulnerability in international communication, where borderless, AI-driven disinformation can directly impact geopolitical stability and diplomatic engagements (Nah et al 2020).

Governments can use AI to deploy highly tailored, transnational propaganda initiatives and international disinformation. AI-powered media can target the unique psychological profiles of users to increase impact and make influence more effective. Furthermore, AI-powered bots and deepfake technologies can artificially amplify specific narratives and construct deceptive content.

This enables contemporary states to engage in a persistent form of informational conflict, with low-cost campaigns that continuously influence the domestic discourse of rival states. AI-tailored media thus allow modern states to achieve strategic objectives while operating below the threshold of conventional warfare. In parallel, analytics powered by AI provide governing bodies with a novel capacity for real-time discernment of international media developments and external public opinion regarding their policies, enabling the pursuit of more dynamic and precisely calibrated diplomatic strategies. However, the technological race also empowers non-state actors, from activist groups to multinational corporations. These groups will increasingly use similar tools and challenge the traditional media dominance of states. The very nature of soft power is thus shifting from the persuasive appeal of culture to the technical prowess of algorithmic distribution and data manipulation. Ultimately, AI is transforming the media from a mere platform for international relations influence into an active, intelligent, and contested battlespace.

Such AI-powered media is playing an increasingly significant role in International Relations by rapidly increasing the flow of information between nations. Positively, AI can enhance diplomatic communication and cross-cultural understanding by powering real-time translation services and facilitating more efficient, data-driven analysis of global media trends for foreign policy makers. Automated analytical technologies will enable diplomats and scholars to identify new international patterns and improve systems that predict potential crises. Through AI-driven monitoring, states can also improve their public diplomacy by adapting communication strategies to diverse international audiences (Bjola and Holmes 2015). However, these benefits are starkly countered by profound negative effects, primarily the strategic weaponisation of AI through social bots and automated accounts that manipulate public opinion, distort the public sphere, and orchestrate disinformation campaigns (Nah et al 2020). AI-generated content can strengthen misinformation campaigns, eroding inter-state trust and heightening geopolitical tensions (Chesney and Citron 2019). The continued use of targeted algorithms can further divide societies by reinforcing echo chambers and influencing political views in ways that are difficult to regulate (Tufekci 2015). Furthermore, authoritarian governments may use AI-enhanced media tools to expand surveillance capabilities and shape narratives that advance their political objectives (Bradshaw and Howard 2019). Eventually, the world risks becoming a place feared by Orwell, where the first victim is truth and objective facts. In that world, two plus two is not necessarily four, everyone believes only in the atrocities of the enemy and not of their own side, and actions are not judged by how good or bad they objectively are, but by who commits them. War becomes peace, freedom is slavery, and ignorance is strength (Orwell 2017).

Automation in media of routine tasks facilitates the high-volume production of data journalism, enhances journalistic practices, and allows cost-effective, tailored adaptation of media content across different linguistic and cultural contexts. On the other hand, the mass generation of algorithmically fabricated media, including deepfakes, creates an asymmetry in scale that exceeds global institutional capacity for authentication. Algorithms enhance content based on individual preferences, increasing engagement and satisfaction. Paradoxically,

content personalisation leads to a dangerous outcome: hyper-personalisation isolates users in ideological bubbles, amplifying extreme views and eroding social cohesion. In the efficient identification and flagging of harmful content, including hate speech, AI systems perform with far greater efficiency than human moderators. This gives rise to dual misuse of AI tools: malicious users exploit AI to falsely flag content, while state actors can weaponize them as instruments for political repression and control. Automated translation and summarisation enhance global communication and understanding by breaking down long-standing language barriers and clarifying dense information. However, the rise of decontextualised information causes the erosion of nuance and results in public misunderstanding of vital issues. Algorithmic curation enables recommendation systems to perform a dual task: identifying user-relevant information and exposing users to a spectrum of media sources. Algorithms optimise content that is sensational, emotive, and divisive, regardless of its veracity. The digital public sphere has assumed prominence as a central arena for information influence in modern geopolitics. AI use in media has fundamentally altered power dynamics and enables state and non-state actors to achieve strategic objectives by leveraging algorithmic biases as instruments of influence. Consequently, the classical imperative to control traditional media has faded. A new generation of creative tools for expressive art, interactive narrative, and experimental media are powerful instruments of “soft power”. These tools have become a powerful strategic narrative that is reshaping International Relations in three main ways:

- 1) Immersive media serve as important tools of modern cultural diplomacy by enabling states and non-state actors to project cultural values, shape global perceptions, and build sentiment. A virtual reality experience of a nation’s heritage often holds more demonstrative power than any formal press release or conventional diplomatic conversation.
- 2) These immersive media tools can be strategically weaponised in geopolitical conflicts, enabling counternarratives, targeted influence on diaspora groups, and more effective manipulation of international public opinion.
- 3) These tools possess a unique transformative capacity to foster deep empathy and urgency among global audiences. They have the potential to translate sentiment into public pressure that shapes governmental decisions on foreign policy, humanitarian assistance, and sanctions regimes.

The ubiquitous presence of AI-generated media systematically undermines epistemic authority, creating a framework in which the authenticity of any digital evidentiary artefact can be questioned due to its potential artificial generation. In summary, although AI-based media offers significant advantages for global information exchange and analysis, it also introduces notable risks that can affect international stability. This degradation of information integrity erodes trust between nations, complicates diplomatic channels, and poses a direct threat to geopolitical stability by enabling foreign interference that can cross borders and undermine sovereign democratic processes.

6 CONCLUSION WITH COMPARATIVE REFLECTIONS ON THE THREE-DIMENSIONAL PARADOXICAL IMPACTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

We have argued and demonstrated in this paper that AI increasingly plays a paradoxical role in international relations by simultaneously producing positive outcomes and less controlled negative effects on relations among key actors. From a historical perspective, this finding is not surprising, as similar effects have accompanied all technological revolutions. However, this paper has shown how the race to adopt AI has specifically begun to unleash competitive forces among states for efficiency, influence, and power across several dimensions. The fundamental assumptions of realist theory align with these paradoxical effects in the military and cyber dimensions. Modern states view the development and deployment of contemporary technologies as a form of self-help that will alter the offence-defence balance. However, such perceptions and efforts systematically undermine the global stability they are intended to achieve. In the defence dimension, we have shown that emerging autonomous systems in all domains – including decision-making, intelligence, targeting, logistics, training, and electronic warfare – have started to enhance national warfare capabilities, while also reinforcing strategic competition among states. It is likely that new AI autonomous systems will be regularly tested in conflicts (such as Ukraine). Each wave of testing will influence regulatory processes, but regulatory processes will likely lag behind technological developments. The AI race will increase international asymmetries in the defence dimension, resulting in more powerful AI-supported states and other, much weaker, peripheral and AI-dependent states.

TABLE 1: PARADOXICAL IMPACT OF AI ON INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS IN THREE DIMENSIONS: DEFENCE, CYBER-SECURITY, AND MEDIA

Military	
Positive Outcomes	Negative Outcomes
Enhanced Strategic Stability	Accelerated Arms Race
Enhanced Targeting Precision and Civilian Protection	Lowering the Cost of War
Improved National Defense and Resilience	AI Driven Crisis Instability
Enhanced Alliance Capabilities	Erosion of Accountability and Norms
Efficiency in Logistics and Peacekeeping	The Rise of Asymmetric AI Threats
Diplomatic Cooperation through Shared Protocols	Fueling Strategic Mistrust and Secrecy
Cyber-security	
Positive Outcomes	Negative Outcomes
Enhanced Defensive Posture	Offensive Arms Race
Improved Attribution	Attribution Problems
Norm Development Catalyst	Erosion of Existing Norms
Power for Smaller States	New Power Asymmetries
Enhanced Crisis Management Tools	Escalation of Destabilizing AI Tools
Securing Global Digital Framework	Weaponization of Interdependence
Media	
Positive Outcomes	Negative Outcomes
Enhanced Content Production	Mass-Production of Disinformation
Personalized User Experience	The Paradox of Personalization
Improved Content Moderation Tools	Adversarial Exploitation and Censorship
Information Accessibility	From Decontextualization to Misinformation
Efficiency in Discovery and Recommendation	Algorithmic Amplification as Instrument of Power
Immersive Media	Erosion of Authenticity and Trust

This paradox is also explained by the security dilemma literature, particularly in the cybersecurity dimension. While AI is creating more powerful offensive and defensive cyber tools, it also increases the likelihood of new conflicts among states and between states and non-state actors, resulting in a new cybersecurity dilemma. Finally, we have demonstrated, also by the use of constructivist theoretical framework, that the use of AI in the media dimension will automate and amplify the production, distribution, and consumption of information and disinformation during peace, crisis, and wartime, influencing public opinion and

discourse. This will expose democratic states to informational, political, and diplomatic conflicts with serious potential effects on inter-state trust and stability. The public sphere risks becoming a more automated media battlespace in the future. International relations will also be affected more indirectly by the proliferation of AI technology to large AI multinational companies and malicious non-state actors in all three studied dimensions. This will further erode the traditional Westphalian system of state sovereignty. The interplay between positive and negative forces identified and analysed above can be synthetically presented in Table 1. The table suggests that improving positive outcomes in the three studied dimensions will inevitably bring negative outcomes. This paradoxical nature of AI will have to be incorporated into future policy making.

AI technology is creating a more complex and unpredictable global landscape, where algorithmic speed and data dominance are becoming strategically important. Understanding the implications of AI in the context of International Relations is essential for shaping future developments towards more cooperative international relations, with less destructive competition for power and influence among states and non-state actors. In other words, this theme is important for future stability and peace. Smaller, poorer, budget-limited, and less technologically developed countries are at risk of increasing dependence on future AI superpowers, which could also exacerbate global inequalities. We recommend the following future research directions in this field: (1) case studies on the application of new AI tools, examining both positive and negative effects; (2) studies on the intensification of the race to adopt AI, focusing on which tools were developed by which countries and the threat perceptions driving these developments – an action-reaction analysis; and (3) investigations into the negative effects of AI-generated content on inter-state relations.

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REFERENCES

- Ackerman, Elliot and James Stavridis. 2024. "Drone Swarms Are About to Change the Balance of Military Power." *Wall Street Journal*, 14 March 2024.
- ADF. 2025. As Drone Warfare Expands in Africa, Turkey Increases Share of the Market, 11 February 2025. Available at <https://adf-magazine.com/2025/02/as-drone-warfare-expands-in-africa-turkey-increases-share-of-the-market/>.
- BBC. 2014. Ted 2014: Edward Snowden on Privacy and NSA Snooping, 19 March 2014. Available at <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-26675445>.
- BBC. 2024. What Are Israel's Iron Dome, David's Sling, Arrow and Thaad Missile Defences?, 16 October 2024. Available at <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-20385306>.
- Bjola, Corneliu and Marcus Holmes. 2015. *Digital Diplomacy: Theory and Practice*. London: Routledge.
- Bradshaw, Samantha and Philip N. Howard. 2019. "The Global Organization of Social Media Disinformation Campaigns." *Journal of International Affairs* 71 (1): 23–32.
- Branch, Jordan. 2018. Technology and Constructivism: Interrogating the Material-Ideational Divide. In *Constructivism Reconsidered: Past, Present, and Future*, eds.

- James, Patrick, Mariano Bertucci and Jarrod Hayes, 103–115. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Bremmer, Ian and Mustafa Suleyman. 2023. "The AI Power Paradox: Can States Learn to Govern Artificial Intelligence – Before It's Too Late?" *Foreign Affairs* 102 (Sep/Oct): 58–72.
- Bresnick, Sam. 2024a. *China's Military AI Roadblocks: PRC Perspectives on Technological Challenges to Intelligentized Warfare*. Washington, DC: CSET Center for Security and Emerging Technology, Georgetown University. Available at <https://cset.georgetown.edu/publication/chinas-military-ai-roadblocks/>.
- Bresnick, Sam. 2024b. "China Bets Big on Military AI." *Center for European Policy Analysis*, 3 April 2024. Available at <https://cepa.org/article/china-bets-big-on-military-ai>.
- Brooks, Harvey. 1980. "Technology, Evolution, and Purpose." *Daedalus* 109 (1): 65–81.
- Burdette, Zachary, David Phillips, John L. Heim, Eliot Geist, David R. Frelinger, Christopher Heitzenrater and Karl P. Mueller. 2025. *An AI Revolution in Military Affairs? How Artificial Intelligence Could Reshape Future Warfare*. WR-A4004-1. Santa Monica, CA: RAND Corporation. Available at https://www.rand.org/pubs/working_papers/WRA4004-1.html.
- Cave, Stephen and Kanta Dihal. 2020. "The Whiteness of AI." *Philosophy & Technology* 33 (4): 685–703.
- Center for Internet Security. 2021. "The SolarWinds Cyber-Attack: What You Need to Know." 15 March 2021. Available at <https://www.cisecurity.org/solarwinds>.
- Chesney, Robert and Danielle Keats Citron. 2019. "Deep Fakes: A Looming Challenge for Privacy, Democracy, and National Security." *California Law Review* 107 (6): 1753–1819.
- Congressional Research Service. 2015. "Cyber Intrusion into U.S. Office of Personnel Management: In Brief." 17 July 2015. Available at <https://www.bing.com>.
- Dahlke, Johannes. 2024. "A.I. Go by Many Names: Towards a Sociotechnical Definition of Artificial Intelligence." *arXiv:2410.13452*.
- Edwards, Jason. 2025. *The Cybersecurity Control Playbook*. New Braunfels: Wiley.
- Entman, Robert M. 2004. *Projections of Power: Framing News, Public Opinion, and U.S. Foreign Policy*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Flournoy, Michèle A. 2023. "AI Is Already at War: How Artificial Intelligence Is Transforming the Military." *Foreign Affairs* 102 (6): 76–91.
- Fravel, M. Taylor, George Gilboy and Eric Heginbotham. 2024. "Estimating China's Defense Spending: How to Get It Wrong and Right." Appendix. Cambridge, MA: MIT Security Studies Program, 1 June 2024. Available at https://ssp.mit.edu/files/ssp/imce/publications/2024/Fravel_Gilboy_Heginbotham_TNSR_Appendix_20240601_UPDATED.pdf.
- Gellman, Barton and Ashkan Soltani. 2013. "NSA Infiltrates Links to Yahoo, Google Data Centers Worldwide, Snowden Documents Say." *The Washington Post*, 30 October 2013.
- Gilboa, Eytan. 2005. "The CNN Effect: The Search for a Communication Theory of International Relations." *Political Communication* 22: 27–44.
- Gross, Leo. 1948. "The Peace of Westphalia, 1648–1948." *The American Journal of International Law* 42 (1): 20–41.
- Herman, Edward S. and Noam Chomsky. 1988. *Manufacturing Consent: The Political Economy of the Mass Media*. New York: Pantheon Books.
- Herz, John. 1950. Idealist Internationalism and the Security Dilemma. *World Politics* 2 (2): 157–180.
- Hodunova, Kateryna. 2025. "Ukrainian Cyber Operatives Disrupt Russian Banking Payment System, Intelligence Source Says." *The Kyiv Independent*, 25 September 2025.
- Jervis, Robert. 1978. Cooperation Under the Security Dilemma. *World Politics*, 30 (2): 167–214.
- Jin, Weina, Nicholas Vincent and Ghassan Hamarneh. 2025. "AI for Just Work: Constructing Diverse Imaginations of AI Beyond 'Replacing Humans.'" *arXiv:2503.08720*.
- Johnson, James. 2023. *AI and the Bomb: Nuclear Strategy and Risk in the Digital Age*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kurzweil, Ray. 1999. *The Age of Spiritual Machines: When Computers Exceed Human Intelligence*. New York: Penguin Putnam Inc.

- Luberisse, Josh. 2023. *The Geopolitics of Artificial Intelligence: Strategic Implications of AI for Global Security*. Wrocław: Fortis Novum Mundum.
- Luknar, Ivana. 2024a. "Artificial Intelligence as a Challenge." *Progress: Journal for Political Theory and Practice* 5 (2): 17–24.
- Luknar, Ivana. 2025a. "The Effect of Technological Progress on the Emergence of Social Deviations Interpreted Through the Issue of Alienation and Technology Dependency." *Sociological Review* 59 (2): 586–609.
- Luknar, Ivana. 2025b. *Socio-Political Effects of Technology*. Belgrade: Institute for Political Studies.
- Metz, Cade. 2018. "As China Marches Forward on A.I., the White House Is Silent." *New York Times*, 12 February 2018.
- Monte, Matthew. 2015. *Network Attacks & Exploitation: A Framework*. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Mowlana, Hamid. 1997. *Global Information and World Communication: New Frontiers in International Relations*. London: Sage Publications.
- Nah, Seungahn, Jasmine McNealy, Jang Hyun Kim and Jisoo Joo. 2020. *Communicating Artificial Intelligence (AI): Theory, Research, and Practice*. New York: Routledge.
- National Security Archive. 2013. "Mandiant, APT 1: Exposing One of China's Cyber Espionage Units." February. Available at <https://nsarchive.gwu.edu/document/21484-document-83>.
- Nye, Joseph S. 2011. *The Future of Power*. New York: PublicAffairs.
- Onuf, Nicholas Greenwood. 1989. *World of Our Making: Rules and Rule in Social Theory and International Relations*. Columbia: University of South Carolina Press.
- Onuf, Nicholas Greenwood. 2013. *Making Sense, Making Worlds: Constructivism in Social Theory and International Relations*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Orwell, George, 2017. *Orwell on Truth*. Reprinted Collection, London: Penguin Books.
- Pangakar, Tajammul. 2025. "Artificial Intelligence in Military Statistics 2025: Efficiency, Tech, Simulations." *Market.us Scoop*, 14 January 2025. Available at <https://scoop.market.us/artificial-intelligence-in-military-statistics>.
- Prezelj, Iztok. 2024a. The Use of Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Systems by Modern Armed Forces and Some Related Concerns. In *Shielding Europe with the Common Security and Defence Policy: The EU Legal Framework for the Development of an Innovative European Defence Industry in Times of a Changing Global Security Environment*, eds. Zombory, Katarzyna and Janos Ede Szilagy, 357–394. Budapest: Central European Academic Publishing.
- Prezelj, Iztok. 2024b. "Challenges in the Use of Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Systems in Modern Armed Forces." *European Integration Studies* 20 (2): 383–408.
- PWC. 2020. Sizing the Prize: What's the Real Value of AI for Your Business and How Can You Capitalise? Available at <https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/issues/analytics/assets/pwc-ai-analysis-sizing-the-prize-report.pdf>.
- Raska, Michael and Richard A. Bitzinger. 2023. Introduction: The AI Wave in Defence Innovation. In *The AI Wave in Defence Innovation: Assessing Military Artificial Intelligence Strategies, Capabilities and Trajectories*, eds. Raska, Michael and Richard A. Bitzinger, 1–11. New York: Routledge.
- Rayman, Noah. 2014. "Report: NSA Spied on Chinese Telecoms Giant." *Time*, 22 March 2014.
- Research and Markets. 2023. Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Military Market by Offering (Software, Hardware, Services), Technology (Machine Learning, Natural Language Processing), Platform (Airborne, Land, Space), Application, Installation Type, Region — Forecast to 2028, 29 May 2023. Available at <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5306656/artificial-intelligence-ai-in-military-market>.
- Rickli, Jean-Marc and Federico Mantellasi. 2023. Artificial Intelligence in Warfare. In *The AI Wave in Defence Innovation: Assessing Military Artificial Intelligence Strategies, Capabilities and Trajectories*, eds. Raska, Michael and Richard A. Bitzinger, 12–36. New York: Routledge.
- Robinson, Piers. 2002. *The CNN Effect: The Myth of News, Foreign Policy and Intervention*. London: Routledge.

- Roth, Melissa. 2019. "Artificial Intelligence at the CIA – Current Applications." *Emerj*, 22 November 2019. Available at <https://emerj.com/ai-sector-overviews/artificial-intelligence-at-the-cia-current-applications>.
- Sanger, David E. 2012. "Obama Order Sped Up Wave of Cyberattacks Against Iran." *The Atlantic Council*, 1 June 2012. Available at <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/natosource/obama-order-sped-up-wave-of-cyberattacks-against-iran>.
- Sanger, David E. and Nicole Perlroth. 2014. "N.S.A. Breached Chinese Servers Seen as Security Threat." *The New York Times*, 22 March 2014.
- Scharre, Paul. 2023. *Four Battlegrounds: Power in the Age of Artificial Intelligence*. First edition. New York: W.W. Norton & Company.
- Soare, Simona. 2023. European Military AI: Why Regional Approaches Are Lagging Behind. In *The AI Wave in Defence Innovation: Assessing Military Artificial Intelligence Strategies, Capabilities and Trajectories*, eds. Raska, Michael and Richard A. Bitzinger, 163–184. New York: Routledge.
- Temple-Raston, Dina. 2021. "A 'Worst Nightmare' Cyberattack: The Untold Story of the SolarWinds Hack." *NPR*, 16 April 2021. Available at <https://www.npr.org/2021/04/16/985439655/a-worst-nightmare-cyberattack-the-untold-story-of-the-solarwinds-hack>.
- The China Briefing. 2025. Briefing: China's Growing Use of Artificial Intelligence in Military Applications, 12 April 2025. Available at <https://thechinabriefing.substack.com/p/briefing-chinas-growing-use-of-artificial>.
- Thiele, Ralph. 2021. Nineteen Technologies in Focus. In *Hybrid Warfare: Future and Technologies*, ed. Thiele, Ralph, 71–124. Wiesbaden: Springer VS.
- Tufekci, Zeynep. 2015. "Algorithmic Harms Beyond Facebook and Google: Emergent Challenges of Computational Agency." *Colorado Technology Law Journal* 13 (1): 203–218.
- Vincent, Brandy. 2024. "Why the Pentagon Didn't Request Higher Funding for AI in Fiscal 2025." *DefenseScoop*, 11 March 2024. Available at <https://defensescoop.com/2024/03/11/pentagon-ai-budget-request-2025>.
- Vinge, Vernor. 1993. "The Coming Technological Singularity: How to Survive in the Post-Human Era." In *Vision 21: Interdisciplinary Science and Engineering in the Era of Cyberspace*. Cleveland, OH: NASA, Lewis Research Center. NASA Technical Reports Server (NTRS). Available at <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/19940022856>.
- Vreg, France. 1990. *Demokratično komuniciranje*. Maribor: Založba Obzorja.
- Waltz, Kenneth. 1979. *Theory of International Politics*. McGraw-Hill.
- Wendt, Alexander. 1992. Anarchy is what states make of it: The social construction of power politics. *International Organization* 46 (2): 391–425.
- Wendt, Alexander. 1999. *Social theory of international politics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Winkel, Marek. 2025. "Controlling the Uncontrollable: The Public Discourse on Artificial Intelligence Between the Positions of Social and Technological Determinism." *AI & Society* 40: 1947–1959.
- Wolff, Josephine. 2021. "How the NotPetya Attack Is Reshaping Cyber Insurance." *Brookings Institution*, 1 December 2021. Available at <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/how-the-notpetya-attack-is-reshaping-cyber-insurance/>.
- Лукнар, Ивана. 2024b. *Вештачка интелигенција: изазови и могућности*. Београд: Медија центар Одбрана.

PARADOKSNI VPLIV UMETNE INTELIGENCE NA MEDNARODNE ODNOSE NA PODROČJU OBRAMBE, KIBERNETSKE VARNOSTI IN MEDIJEV

Umetna inteligenca (UI) hitro postaja ključni katalizator preobrazbe znotraj mednarodnega sistema. UI ponuja tako pomemben potencial kot resna tveganja, kar države motivira, da uravnotežijo izjemne priložnosti z velikimi izzivi. Glavni cilj članka je analizirati in predstaviti, kako tehnologije UI in njihova paradoksalna družbeno-tehnična narava spreminjajo mednarodne odnose s pospeševanjem globalne nestabilnosti in varnostnih groženj ter ustvarjanjem novih vektorjev moči, ranljivosti in vpliva. Članek analizira preobrazbene vplive v treh ključnih dimenzijah: obrambi, kibernetiki varnosti in medijih. V obrambni dimenziji prikazuje, da bodo nastajajoči avtonomni sistemi na vseh področjih znatno izboljšali nacionalne vojaške zmogljivosti, hkrati pa bodo okrepiли strateško konkurenco med državami z epizodnimi preizkusi v živo v konfliktih in povečali strateško odvisnost manj sposobnih držav. Umetna inteligenca bo ustvarila tudi močnejša ofenzivna in obrambna kibernetična orodja, kar bo povzročilo novo dilemo na področju kibernetične varnosti, povečalo verjetnost novih konfliktov in opolnomočilo nedržavne kriminalne akterje. Poleg tega bo umetna inteligenca v medijski dimenziji avtomatizirala in okrepiła proizvodnjo, distribucijo in porabo informacij in dezinformacij v miru, krizah in vojni, s čimer bo vplivala na javno mnenje in diskurz ter izpostavila demokratične države informacijskim, političnim in diplomatskim konfliktom, ki bi lahko imeli resne posledice za meddržavno zaupanje in stabilnost.

Ključne besede: umetna inteligenca; mednarodni odnosi; obramba; kibernetična varnost; mediji.